

IJMSBR

<https://www.ijmsbr.com/>

Impact Factor: 6.049

A Digital Maturity Model for Electronics Manufacturing Firms toward Servitization with Integrated Approach

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Abstract

The global trend of digital technologies and the COVID-19 pandemic have made the growth speed of digital transformation (DT), one of the most popular trends for enterprises worldwide so far, steadier than ever. The specific difficulties in adapting to this new approach pose challenges for Electronics Industry (EI) firms, especially in developing countries like Vietnam, where these companies contribute a significant proportion of Vietnam GDP, up to 40 percent in 2021 (MoIT, 2021). In order to implement a digital evolutionary path appropriately, tools such as the Digital Maturity Model (DMM) can be handy since they help companies evaluate their initial states and plan development road maps (Rafael et al., 2020). Over the last few years, several DMMs geared towards Industry 4.0 have been created and released, some of which are specifically aimed at cross-industry or specific sectors, including manufacturing. However, none of them is specially developed for an industry of such vital importance as the EI sector, especially guide it embraces the Servitization trend. This article presents a new DMM to lead EI companies to Servitization align with both of Product Service System (PPS) and Service Design approach, with its development is based on the design science research methodology (Becker et al., 2009). A joint-venture telecom equipment company under VNPT, the biggest telecommunication service provider in Vietnam, was chosen as a case study for joining the DMM development process. For the next step, the authors decided that the newly developed DMM should be evaluated to gain excellent results for the incumbent firm and then disseminated to more companies to become a standardized DMM for the sector.

Keywords: digital transformation, digital maturity model, change management, Electronics Industry, Servitization, Product Service System, PSS, Service Design.

1. Introduction

The fourth industrial revolution with digital technologies disruptions transforms traditional manufacturing companies into Smart Factories. They are capable of capturing, processing, and delivering data, making decentralized decisions and even acting as self-control systems through communication devices, warehouse systems, 3-D printing, sensors, radio-frequency identification (RFID) tags, interfaces, actuators, etc. (Brettel et al. 2014). These allow for bidirectional communication and synchronization between the physical (humans, products, and machines) and virtual worlds. Indeed, the digital transformation (DT) should generate (Henning et

al., 2013): i) Improved vertical integration of systems, information, resources, flows between all departmental and hierarchical levels in internal departments within a firm; ii) Improved horizontal integration between entities within a value chain; iii) Improved end-to-end digital integration between entities and product life cycle to offer up-to-date products to meet every customer's requirement.

The complexity of adopting Industry 4.0 drives to follow a customized Digital Maturity Model (DMM) to guide managers in the process. The DMM should perfectly fit with the distinctive character of the sector (Piccarozzi et al., 2018) and contextual characteristics of adopter firms (Colli et al., 2019). However, even though most existing DMM is for the manufacturing sector, there is no evidence of a specific DMM aimed at the Electronics Industry (EI) sector, a sub-sector of manufacturing but plays a substantial role in the global economy. Hence, EI firms lack guidance in successfully embracing Industry 4.0 technologies and practices in their firms to transform their product and business models to gain competitiveness over rivals.

Accordingly, this article attempts to fill this gap by pursuing the implementation of a DMM with a normative purpose targeting the EI sector. The model, called EI-DMM, is developed by following the well-known procedure model of Becker et al. (2009). By addressing the above goal, this evolutionary roadmap will require a comprehensive view of the Industry 4.0 paradigm and its related DMM in addition to the specifics of the EI sector. The targeted DMM will be evaluated through a case study of an EI firm under one of the most prominent telecommunication groups in Vietnam.

The remainder of this article is organized as follows. Section 2 introduces the theoretical background underpinning the research by outlining characteristics of Industry 4.0, EI sector, and their concerns in the implementation of Industry 4.0. Section 2 also reviews the existing models as a guide to adopting Industry 4.0 and states the need and opportunity to develop a DMM for the EI sector. Section 3 explains the research methodology followed to implement the Industry 4.0 MM targeted at the said sector. Section 4 and 5 formulate the main characteristics of the EI-DMM. Lastly, Section 6 summarizes the main findings and contributions of the research and suggestions for possible future issues.

2. Theoretical background

2.1 Electronics Industry (EI) sector in Industry 4.0

The term Industry 4.0 (I4.0) was introduced by a German initiative in 2011 to develop advanced production systems based on digitalization and automation of the manufacturing environment (Oesterreich and Teuteberg, 2016) increase the productivity and efficiency of the national industry (Frank et al., 2019). The digitalization is seen as the integration and optimization of information (Bogner et al., 2016) and integration of vertical and horizontal value chains (Geissbauer et al., 2016), and has a significant impact on firms' existing processes and capabilities. It is considered as a facilitator and an essential requirement to reach I4.0 (Schuh et al., 2017).

In addition, the I4.0 also innovates business models mainly due to providing a transformational environment, knowledge management, and supply chain capacity building. I4.0 involves more than just designing a new strategy; corporate culture, management approaches, the role of information technology (IT), and innovation engines must be re-examined and often revamped (Schrauf & Bertram, 2016). Emerging manufacturing technologies are needed to reduce production time to move products to the market more rapidly and efficiently than competitors to attain operational excellence (Ahmad et al., 2018; Kristianto et al., 2012). I4.0 deployment has generated a new manufacturing working environment, changing traditional skills. It also makes employees survival depend on their degree of adaptability to new job requirements (e.g., non-technical skills, and data analytics) (Lichtblau et al., 2015; Sony, 2019).

In the context of the electronics manufacturing sector, The I4.0 nowadays has a strong effect on the E&E manufacturing companies. Manufacturing companies such as electrical and electronics (E&E) today face paramount pressures to improve their operations, such as ensuring costs reduction, flexibility, short lead-time

delivery, legal, environmental, and social requirements compliance, e.g. (Ahmad et al., 2018). A critical strategic issue pursued by these companies has been to shift competition further into other dimensions than price, by investing in new products, technology, and services, have a greater level of transparency (Kamp et al., 2017). Regarding technology, as the demand for high-performing electronics equipment is increasing, electronics manufacturers are adopting emerging technologies like SMACIT (Warner & Wäger, 2019), smart devices to improve efficiency, connectivity, and productivity and satisfy complex customer needs (Gilchrist, 2016). In addition, such new technologies give firms more opportunities to offer more services. Regarding services, Servitization is typically a strategic response by electronics manufacturing companies to transform them from only selling products to instead adding additional value by including various services within the product offerings (Vandermerwe and Rada, 1988). Servitization helps manufacturers reach the maturity phase in the product lifecycle and gain profit over the entire product lifecycle (Kowalkowski et al., 2017). In Servitization, the Product-Service System (PSS) approach and Service design approach is recommended to be implemented in an *integrated manner* to combine the human-centered and co-creative perspectives from Service Design (Wetter-Edman et al., 2014) and the product and organizational networks perspective from PSS (Costa et al., 2016).

In particular, Vietnam electronics industry is an increasingly important sector of the country's economy when taking the lead in export turnover among industries. It has accounted for nearly 40 percent of the national GDP in recent years (MoIT, 2021). Vietnam is one of the world's key electronics exporters, ranking 12th in the world since 2015, and the export volume steadily climbed from \$47.3 billion in 2015 to \$96.9 billion in 2019 (Nguyen, 2021). Vietnam's electronics exports continue to grow despite the negative impact of the COVID-19 pandemic, climbing 12% to nearly 100 billion in 2020 (MoIT, 2021). However, Vietnam's EI sector faces significant challenges in maintaining growth with growing competition from Taiwan, Singapore, China, and other Asian countries. Incredibly, most electronics manufacturers in Vietnam are Electronic Manufacturing Service (EMS) companies, focusing on providing outsourced production facilities, labor, and procurement services for international electronics equipment producers (Ngoc & Binh, 2019). Hence, they show low production efficiency and poor value-added services, with the profitability of those sectors ranging relatively low from about 5 to 10 percent (Ngoc & Binh, 2019). Therefore, to ensure their survival and growth in the market, Vietnamese EI enterprises need to have new capabilities to pursue digital transformation toward servitization. Managers need to build their internal competencies to deal with issues, changes, and strategies. However, there is a lack of a proven DMM for Electronics Industry with the previously mentioned requirements. Therefore, and because of the significance of this enabler sector, it would be beneficial to design, develop and test a DMM fitted to this industry where digital servitization, together with the other dimensions, is gaining great significance.

2.2 Foundation of digital maturity model

The concept of maturity model (MM) first appeared in the 1970s and is dedicated to software engineering (Rafael et al., 2020). Since then, the MM concept has evolved into an essential tool for improving business practices (Schäffer et al., 2018) by assessing their status-quos, establishing a desirable path for advancing them, and making internal or external benchmarking to realize gaps in competencies manner (Röglinger et al., 2012). MMs have gained popularity in management and science (Becker et al., 2009; Rafael et al., 2020) with a broad range of potential applications. There are lots of MMs that have been published focusing on different fields of organizations' capabilities such as "IT service capability, innovation management, program management, enterprise architecture, strategic alignment, or knowledge management maturity" (De Bruin et al., 2005), Process Management (ISO, 2015), Enterprise Integration (ISO, 2007). The most well-known MM is the Capability Maturity Model (CMM) derived from Phillip Crosby's Quality Management Maturity Grid (QMMG) model, which aims to help evaluate the quality of the information systems and processes (Williams et al., 2019). Meanwhile, the DT is a modern revolution where companies use new digital technologies such as SMACIT (Warner and Wäger, 2019) to enable significant business improvements like enhancing customer experience,

advancing operations excellence, and innovating new business models (Fitzgerald et al., 2014). It is a strategic change that needs to be aligned with several aspects (Singh & Hess, 2017), such as operational, functional, financial, and corporate strategy (Matt et al., 2015). However, all previously mentioned MMs just applied in improving specific organizations' capabilities, which means there is a need to develop a maturity model that covers the number of capabilities required for the DT (Kane, 2017). The Digital Maturity Model (DMM) is a type of MM that focuses on supporting firms to assess and develop their digital capabilities (Becker et al., 2009). MMs are reference models that deal with identifying the organizations' current state (AS-IS) and the evolution of maturity to target state (TO-BE) (Pöppelbuß and Röglinger 2011). Development states are synonymous with maturity levels. The change to a higher level of maturity is equivalent to an improvement in DT (Leyh et al., 2016). With the booming of the DT trend, DMM has become one of the most important fields for both academia and practitioners to research and pursue.

Figure 1. Components and characteristics of maturity models. Source: Hoang & Hong (2022).

The *components* and *characteristics* of DMMs are depicted in Figure 1. The most important characteristics of DMMs are purposes, scope, approach type, source. The *purpose* attribute includes descriptive, prescriptive, and comparative functions (Röglinger et al., 2012). The *descriptive* function is suggested to conduct to a contextualized context so that the *prescriptive* function can give context-specific recommendations for firms that have similar digital maturity levels (Colli et al., 2019). The *comparative* purpose enables benchmarking across companies or capabilities between business units and organizations (Felch et al., 2019). DMMs' scopes can cover a *specific* industry or *cross-industries* so that firms decide to select an appropriate DMM for them. DMMs' approach can cover *specific* capabilities that the firms are concerned with or all capabilities (*multi-dimensions*) they need to advance to digital enterprises (Schumacher et al., 2019). There are four primary *sources* of DMMs creating (Schallmo et al., 2020): Consultancy, Associations, Scientific, Big companies, where 70% of models are developed by Practitioners (Canetta et al., 2018).

The popular components used to construct DMMs compose maturity level, dimension, capabilities, scale items, requirements. First, MMs can depict a sequence of discrete levels, i.e., dimensions and capabilities (Pöppelbuss and Röglinger, 2011) to support reporting to layers of management and enabling maturity level improvements management (De Bruin et al., 2005). *Dimensions* (focus areas, or action fields, or domains) are essential and fundamental business areas impacted by DT (Rafael et al., 2020). The most popular dimensions are Culture, Customer, Data, Digital Technology, Innovation, IT Technology, Organization, Partner, People, Process, Product, Strategy, Transformation Management (Hoang and Hong, 2022) as depict in Table 1. Sub-Dimensions, usually called *capabilities*, are prominent, independent aspects of a given domain that is important

to domain maturity e.g., strategic capabilities, critical success factors (El Sawy et al., 2016), resistances to entry higher maturity level (De Bruin et al., 2005). *Scale Items* of capabilities are specific characteristics of capabilities that provide further detail enabling targeted maturity level improvements (De Bruin et al., 2005). *Maturity levels* represent archetypal states of maturity of a particular dimension (Rafael et al., 2020). Standardized maturity levels are the basis of a *benchmarking* approach between companies (Puchan et al., 2018). There are two scale types for maturity levels: fixed levels and focus area (Häckel et al., 2021): Maturity in the form of *fixed levels* is a rather classic approach, where the five-level scale is most common. These fixed levels can be either (i) staged or (ii) continuous. The *staged* one requires an assignment of capabilities to exactly one maturity stage. On the other hand, the *continuous* one requires the specification of capabilities for all maturity stages (Häckel et al., 2021); In the *focus area* maturity models, each capability area has its number of specific maturity stages in terms of quantity and distance to each other (Häckel et al., 2021). About the *requirements*, according to, DMMs should fulfil the normative defined for standardized MMs like (ISO, 2007; 2015) such as completeness, clarity, and unambiguity to ensure that gaining objective, impartial, consistent, repeatable, comparable, and representative results of the assessed organizational units (Rafael et al., 2020).

Table 1. Comparison of well-known digital maturity models. Source: Hoang & Hong (2022).

Legend: A: Academy, O: Organisation; C: Cross-Industry, S: Specific Industry; o/x – DMM (does not) have sub-dimensions; *: weighting

No.	DMM	Author/s	Year	Source	Scope	Dimensions												
						Size	Culture	Customer	Data	Digital Technologies	IT Technology	Innovation	Organisation	Partner	People	Process	Products	Strategy
1	Product-Service Systems Maturity Model	Häckel et al. (2021)	2021	A	S	4	x	x	x		x		x	x	x	x	x	
2	Maturity Model for Machine Tool Company	Rafael et al. (2020)	2020	A	S	6			x				x		x	x	x	
3	Smart Industry Readiness Index*	SIRI (2019)	2019	O	S	5			x		x		x		x	x	x	
4	ACATECH Industries 4.0 Maturity Index	Schuh et al. (2018)	2018	A	S	6	x		x	x	x		x		x	x		
5	Maturity Model for Leveraging Digitalization in Manufacturing	Sjödin et al. (2018)	2018	A	S	3	o		o		o			o	o	o		
6	MM for Assessing the Digital Readiness of Manufacturing Companies	De Carolis et al. (2017a)	2017	A	S	4	x				x		x			x		
7	IMPULS	Lichtblau et al. (2017)	2017	A	S	6			x	x			x		x	x	x	x
8	MMfor Industry 4.0 Readiness and Maturity	Schumacher et al. (2016)	2016	A	S	7	x	x			x		x		x		x	x
Total (Manufacturing sector)						5	2	6	2	6	0	7	2	7	7	5	4	0
9	TM Forum’s Digital Maturity Model (4.0.3)	TM Forum (2021)	2021	O	C	10	x	x	x	x	x		x	x	x	x	x	
10	Multi-dimensional Maturity Model	Berger et al. (2020)	2020	A	C	7	x	x	x	x				x	x	x		x
11	Structuring Digital Transformation	Gimpel et al. (2018)	2018	A	C	8		x	x	x			x	x		x	x	x
12	Digital Maturity	Rossmann (2018)	2018	A	C	7	o		o		o		o		o	o	o	o
13	Open Digital Maturity Model (ODMM)*	Open ROADS (2017)	2017	O	C	10	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x		x	x
14	Digital Business Transformation Stages	Berghaus & Back (2016)	2016	A	C	10	x	x	x		x	x	x		x	x	x	x
Total (Cross-industry)						5	5	6	4	4	2	5	4	5	5	5	6	2
Total (Manufacturing sector & Cross-industry)						10	7	12	6	10	2	12	7	12	13	11	10	2

3. Research Methodology and Development Process of EI-DMM

The development applies the design science research methodology (DSRM) paradigm established and well-accepted in IS research (Hevner et al., 2004). The paradigm provides a proven rigor methodology for developing novel artifacts to support users and organizations (Hevner et al., 2004). To develop our DMM, we follow the eight-step procedure for the model development from Becker et al. (2009) based on the DSRM paradigm (Figure 2). The first four phases are central to the design and development of the MM (Table 2) and are this work's focus. The other phases that cover the transfer and evaluation will be carried out in future research because it requires further continuous evaluation to ensure rigorous evaluation (Poeppebus and Röglinger, 2011).

Figure 2. Research approach for EI-DMM development based on Becker et al. (2009).

The first phase, Problem definition, examines the motivation for the MM that comprises the determinations and problems of the application areas. The second phase, Comparing existing MMs, reviews existing publications to point towards research gaps. The third phase, Determination of Development Strategy, comprises four strategies, i.e., design of new model design, enhancement of an existing model, a combination of models to form a new one, and the transfer of existing models to new application domains (Becker et al., 2009). The Iterative Maturity Model's fourth phase is the central one of the procedure models. Some additional techniques are recommended to develop a proper research and practice model within this phase. For example, using the multi-methodological approach (van Steenbergen et al., 2010), including literature reviews and expert interviews with co-author and scientific focus group discussions, distinguishes between a conceptual-to-empirical empirical-to-conceptual approach (Nickerson et al., 2013). literature and the researchers' knowledge are focused on the deductive conceptual-to-empirical approach. At the same time, the practical perspective and adjusting the artifact is mainly used in the inductive empirical-to-conceptual approach (Nickerson et al., 2013). The fifth one, the Conception of transfer and evaluation, focuses on model evaluation to ensure the proposal MM is accessible for intended users. The sixth phase, Implementation of the transfer media, help the MM appropriately accessible to target user groups. In the seventh phase, the MM is applied for target user groups

and examined whether the MM delivers the aspired solution of the problem. Lastly, in the eighth phase, Decision about Rejection of Maturity Model, the MM is rejected if it is out of date or does not function well.

This work focuses on the first four DMM design and development phases. In Section 2, 3 first phases are conducted: The need for EI sectors management guidance is examined, where the critical problem is that EI firms face significant challenges in developing toward a PSS provider, especially those under telecommunication service providers (Phase 1). While existing MMs for EI neglect a holistic perspective on the organization, we propose our EI-DMM to fill this gap (Phase 2). At the phase of determination of the development strategy (Phase 3), there is no MM in the literature, which identifies all relevant dimensions for the DT of the EI sector. However, several existing models were close enough to be combined (Strategy 3) that could fulfill the gap.

Iteration	Approach	Activity	Deliverables
I1	conceptual-to-empirical	Literature review of existing DMMs	First draft of capability framework
I2	conceptual-to-empirical	Literature review for EI characteristics	First draft of the digital maturity model with most defined maturity levels of capabilities
I3	empirical-to-conceptual	Interview scholars	The complete digital maturity model
I4	empirical-to-conceptual	Focus group discussion (pre-evaluation)	Pre-evaluated digital maturity model

Table 2. Iterations’ activities and Deliverables of model development phase. Source: Berker et al. (2009)

Within *Phase 4*, the Iterative MM development, as mentioned above, a multi-methodological approach for developing dimension-specific development paths is conducted (van Steenberg et al., 2010). In *Iteration one*, the literature search, we identified existing MMs focused on manufacturing and related to the research stream (EMS or PSS) as recommended by Becker et al. (2009). For this, we performed a search on Google Scholar with the following search string: *"Digital transformation" OR "digital maturity" "maturity model" OR "readiness index."* The authors limit sources of papers in several well-known databases, including Elsevier, EBSCOhost, Emerald, Taylor & Francis, AIS eLibrary, IEEE, ResearchGate. We only considered results as articles in English, not literature review ones and for enterprises. As a result, we found 82 papers where 35 related to MMs in which 15 MMs are for manufacturing (e.g., Hackel et al. (2021); Rafael et al. (2020), Schumacher et al. (2016)), and 10 MMs are for cross-industry (e.g., Berger et al. (2020), Berghaus & Back (2016), Gimpel et al. (2018)). To understand and build upon existing work, as recommended by Becker et al. (2009), we compared these MMs and partly included them in our MM by identifying relevant capabilities for EI. This bottom-up approach identified 180 capabilities from manufacturing MMs for the EI sector. After coding and clustering these capabilities, we came up with 155 capabilities. To enhance clarity and accessibility, we cluster these capabilities into seven dimensions. As we supplement our findings with existing frameworks, e.g., Häckel et al. (2021), we create awareness of the dimensions' interrelations. We iteratively refine the dimensions and capabilities until we achieve consensus among the research team.

Next, within *Iteration two*, we carried out a literature review for EI and additional capabilities to ensure that the body of knowledge is covered by existing MMs on EI and recent and domain-specific work. Hence, we applied this by assessing domain-related databases, i.e., ScienceDirect, EBSCOhost, and AISEL, with the following search string: *"Electronics Industry" OR "Electronics Manufacturing" OR "Electronics Manufacturer" AND "digital transformation."* Thereby, we reviewed 70 articles to identify EI capabilities required for digital transformation. Furthermore, we finished with a forward and backward search to screen the field of research and completed the maturity levels. After carefully reading and screening these publications, we worked out and coded another 23 capabilities from this general EI literature.

In these first two iterations, 178 capabilities (155 + 23) were found and processed (coded and clustered). After reducing the duplicates and summarizing similar ones, 38 capabilities were finally derived (32 from existing

MMs and 6 from EI literature). The definition of all maturity levels, including different characteristics, is required to outline each capability dimension's maturation along all stages. We proceeded by using the literature and more specified capabilities.

After developing the second version of the EI-DMM and intensively discussing it within the research team, *Iteration three* conducted two separate interviews with EI experts to clarify its dimensions, capabilities, and characteristics of capabilities for each maturity level. One expert is expertise in automation production (IP1), and the other is in digital business strategies for manufacturers (IP2). The interview partners are summarized in Table 3. After these interviews, the team critically discussed proposed model adjustments before including them in the EI DMM.

IP	Type	Job Title	Industry	Expertise	Experiences
IP1	Interview Partner	Senior Manager Digitalization	Electronics Industry Manufacturing	PPS, CPS, IoT, Autonomous Operation	Senior manager (> 15 years in this field)
IP2	Interview Partner	Head of Digital Business	Telecommunication Equipment Manufacturing	Supply Chain Management, Digital Marketing	Senior manager (> 15 years in this field)
FG1	Focus Group	Deputy Dean of Economic & Management	Economic & Management	Business transformation, high performance manufacturing	Senior researcher (> 15 years in this field)
FG2	Focus Group	Deputy Director of Department for Human and Social Development Strategies	Business Administration	Transformation strategies for manufacturers; Planning and Investment	Senior researcher (> 15 years in this field)
FG3	Focus Group	PhD student	Domain focus on Industry 4.0, Telecom	Digital Transformation, Change Management	Senior researcher (> 5 years in this field)
FG4	Focus Group	ICT Expert	Domain focus on Industry 4.0	Enterprise Architect, Digital Technology	Senior expert (> 5 years in this field)
FG5	Focus Group	Digital Transformation Consultant	Domain focus on Industry 4.0, Digital Transformation	DMM development	Senior expert (> 5 years in this field)
FG6	Focus Group	PhD student	Domain focus on Industry 4.0, DMM, Manufacturing	Knowledge and Innovation Management	Junior researcher (<2 years in this field)

Table 3. Development team for model development phase.

At *Iteration four*, as the interviews brought no significant recommendations, the MM was pre-evaluated in a focus group discussion with six domain-specific scholars specialized in EI and related fields (FG1-6 in Table 3). Thereby, the focus group evaluated the DMM using the proposed criteria of Becker et al. (2009). After the focus group agrees that the DMM is comprehensive, concise, and robust, the development process (Phase 4) is complete. This pre-evaluation DMM is explained in detail in Section 5.

4. Digital Maturity Model for Electronics Industry (EI-DMM)

In the following, the core of this paperwork, we present the EI-DMM in two main themes: Maturity scale and Dimensions. Regarding the Maturity scale, the model uses the concept of capability maturity model (CMM) (Team, 2006) and recommendations from giant practitioners like Cognizant (Corver & Elkhuzen, 2014), PwC (Geissbauer et al., 2016), and Red Hat (Whitehurst, 2017). Moreover, the development team expands it in several aspects to cover the scale of the most well-known TM Forum’s DMM (2021) as a de-facto standard. This means the development DMM has more chance in integrating with the DMM of the firm’s parents, and/or

benchmarking with other peers. Using these principles, the authors define five maturity levels as below (Table 4):

Level	Name	Definition
1	Initiating	No Industry 4.0 or only “ad-hoc”: There is some individual initiatives but no person explicitly responsible for industry 4.0 or digital transformation, and, most importantly, no existing clear vision has been formulated regarding those topics. Consequently, there are no well-defined processes or supporting systems.
2	Emerging	Project level: digital transformation is seen as a technical or production problem that is being handled in few pioneer Projects. There are still no well-defined processes or supporting systems.
3	Performing	Departmental level (isolated silos): digital transformation is seen as a technical or production problem need to be processed on departmental or shop floor level. Yet, there is no global vision to coordinate and synchronise these activities. In many cases, the IT or production/engineering departments are the first ones to look for digital transformation and Industry 4.0 adoption.
4	Advancing	Organizational level (cross-departmental): Organizational level (cross-departmental): Digital transformation is being handled as a business problem that needs all departments involved in defining this vision and formulating the digital strategy in the manner of an overall vision and integrative approach
5	Leading	Inter-organizational level (cross supply chain/value chain partners): Digital transformation is seen here as a business issue on the overall value/supply chain. Consequently, defining the digital transformation/Industry 4.0 vision and strategy should consider the complexity and needs of the value/supply chain partners. The processes and use cases are defined to go beyond the organizational borders to enable collaboration with those partners. This will allow the transparency and intelligence required to make appropriate decisions regarding production and/or products.

Table 4. Maturity of development model for EI sector (EI-DMM).

Regarding the model’s structure components, the development teams address required capabilities for the corresponding manufacturers (Lichtblau et al, 2017; SIRI, 2017), PSS Provider (Hackel et al., 2021), Service Provider (Open ROADS, 2021; TM Forum, 2021). Moreover, the development team supplements them in aspects to cover critical fields that typical firms must consider in digital transformation like Customer, Strategy, & Organisation (Berger et al., 2020; Berghaus and Back, 2016; Gimpel et al., 2018; Schumacher et al., 2019; Westerman et al., 2014). This means the development DMM has ability of address root cause of the incumbent firm’s weakness, without a need to perform further assessment by other multi-dimension models (Gajsek et al., 2019). Using these principles, the authors define seven dimensions for the EI-DMM as depicted in (Table 5), (the detail sub-dimensions and attributes are depicted in Appendix 1):

Dimensions (Domains)	Definition	References
People & Culture	The workforce with proper qualification and constant updating of the technical and management skills is crucial for digital transformation and the intensive use of innovative technologies. The teams need to have PPS thinking, opened for innovative technologies, and to have flexibility and autonomy for fast changes in context. These supported by the promotion and dissemination of an innovative culture, digital workplace environment, and digital leadership.	Berghaus and Back (2016), Bilgeri et al. (2017), El Sawy et al. (2016), Gimpel et al. (2018), Häckel et al. (2021), Kane et al. (2015, 2016, 2017), Schuh et al. (2017)
Data	Data to be the "new oil" in the digital economy, the foundation of success for many actions fields related to digital transformation. Data need to be collected and aggregated so that they become available in standard forms, unprecedented volume, variety, and velocity. By exploiting data via advanced analytics an organization can insight customer or operations, predict usage, support decision making. Those capabilities must be implemented across the value chain, not only intra the	Colli et al. (2019), Gimpel et al. (2018), Häckel et al. (2021), Schuh et al. (2017), Schumacher et al. (2019)

	organization but integrated with ecosystem partners to provide best experience to customer.	
Smart Products	Products with ICT add-ons enabling data acquisition, continuous connectivity and communication with customers, factory across the value chain. Complementary services will be an important source of the company's revenue by result-based payment	Arnold et al. (2016), Berger et al. (2020), Holotiuk and Beimborn (2017), Häckel et al. (2021), Lichtblau et al. (2015), Rafael et al. (2020)
Smart Operation	The autonomous systems and processes based on connectivity and interoperability of information between operation systems, equipment, and installations. These allow self-optimization and self-configuration of processes of production, maintenance, logistics. It supports fast development cycles and prototyping and continuous improvement of production.	Berghaus and Back (2016), Colli et al. (2019), El Sawy et al. (2016), Gimpel et al. (2018), Häckel et al., (2021) Kane et al. (2016), Lichtblau et al. (2015), Schuh et al. (2017), Schumacher et al. (2019)
Smart Factory	The cloud-based factories with fully IT security activities, and IT infrastructures as enablers of production. Smart sensors, digital modelling will enable the communication in real time between machines, installations and people forming a digital network environment.	Berghaus & Back (2016), Colli et al. (2019), El Sawy et al. (2016), Gimpel et al. (2018), Häckel et al. (2021), Rafael et al. (2020), Schuh et al. (2017)
Strategy & Organisation	The evolution toward Industry 4.0 needs a change of paradigms of the administration board through the Offering and Pricing Strategy, product as point-of-sale vision, the adequacy of the partner networking and organizational structure, the disposability of required resources to functioning PPS.	Berghaus and Back (2016), Colli et al. (2019), El Sawy et al. (2016), Gimpel et al. (2018), Häckel et al. (2021), Kane et al. (2016) Schumacher et al. (2019)
Customer	In the digital economy, customer experience is vital to gain and sustain customer relationships. Customer insight and customer interaction are important for improving and personalized service to customer. The digital product welcomes customers as partners to co-create new disruptions.	Arnold et al. (2016), Berghaus and Back (2016), Exner et al. (2018), Fleisch et al. (2015), Gimpel et al. (2018), Holotiuk and Beimborn (2017), Häckel et al. (2021), Kiel et al. (2017), Schumacher et al. (2019), Westerman et al. (2014), Übelhör (2019)

Table 5. Dimensions of the development model for EI sector (EI-DMM).

5. Pre-evaluation

As recommended in the development process of Becker et al. (2009), we evaluated our EI-DMM using proposed evaluation criteria. We conducted a pre-evaluation of the model to anticipate a demonstration and application of the model in practice to first assess the model's quality according to recommended criteria. A comprehensive application and demonstration of the model in practice with industry experts, as proposed by Becker et al. (2009), is planned to be subject to further research. Therefore, our theoretical evaluation was carried out through a focus group discussion with domain-specific scholars of Operation Management field. We used the evaluation criteria of Becker et al. (2009), which are: (1) comprehensiveness, (2) consistency, and (3) problem adequacy. The focus group comprised nine research scholars with experience in EI, PSS, Service Design and DMM development (see Table 3):

- (1) Comprehensiveness: Within the focus group, the model was perceived as comprehensive and covering essential EI, PSS, Service Design aspects.
- (2) Consistency: The focus group generally agreed on the overall consistency but objected to a few minor issues. Minor adjustments for name of dimensions and sub-dimensions were made.
- (3) Problem adequacy: The focus group discussion led to several iterations of the model, which resulted in an improved specificity for the application context.

6. Conclusion

This paper addresses the need and develops EI-DMM, a DMM to guide electronics manufacturers digitally transforming them toward Servitization. To structure the EI-DMM, the authors have performed a review of DMM theory, addressing Servitization as a business model that electronics manufacturers should pursue with an

integrated PSS and Service Design approach. We followed design science research methodology (DSRM) from Becker et al. (2009) for the MM development. We iteratively developed the model by conducting expert interviews with senior scholars by building upon the literature. We pre-evaluated the EI-DMM with domain-specific scholars by checking for the proposed evaluation criteria (i.e., comprehensiveness, consistency, problem adequacy) of Becker et al. (2009) in a focus group discussion. Our contribution is relevant for practice and research. Regarding the practice aspect, within Vietnam's particular context, the paperwork has extended (Ngoc and Binh, 2019) research in improving the efficiency and probability of Vietnamese EI firms that are relatively low. It points out that these firms should consider and digitally transform them toward Servitization model under an integrated PSS and Service Design approach. Regarding the research aspect, this paper seriously followed the MM development procedure of Becker et al. (2009) to gain high quality. Besides developing a new DMM for a specific sector and pre-evaluated with scholars and a top Vietnamese EI company, the paper provides a foundation for future research on performing a massive evaluation to more companies to improve it and make it a standardized DMM for the EI sector./.

Funding

This research is funded by Vietnam National Foundation for Science and Technology Development (NAFOSTED) under grant number 502.01-2018.26.

Acknowledgments

This research is supported by HUST University¹, VNPT Group².

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Appendix 1. Structured components of EI-DMM, the digital maturity model for EI sectors.

Domain	Capabilities	Maturity Levels				
		1-Initiating	2-Emerging	3-Performing	4-Advancing	5-Leading
Operational Capabilities	Digital Skills	No Digital Skills	Recruiting Digital Skills	Educating Digital Skills	Developing Digital Talents	Developing Digital Leaders
	PSS vision engagement	Product-oriented way of thinking	Thinking of offering complementary services	Thinking in terms of customer usage;	Thinking of providing PSS solutions	Thinking of delivering result as a service
	Workplace Environment	Desk Space	Meeting and Social Space	Collaborative Space	Spaces beyond the Building	Digital Workplace
	Innovation Culture	Inhibition of Innovation	Openness towards Change	Acknowledgement of Experimentation	Aspiration to Improvements	Entrepreneurial Thinking
	Leadership	Top-Down Governance	Transformational Leadership	Servant Leadership	Coaches & Sponsors	Digital Leadership
Data Capabilities	Data Collection	No Collection	Manual Collection	Partially Automated Collection	Fully Automated Collection	Automated Collection with ecosystem partners
	Data Aggregation	Raw Data	Target Data	Pre-processed Data	Transformed Data	Enrichment Data
	Data Analysis	No Analysis	Descriptive Analysis	Diagnostic Analysis	Predictive Analysis	Prescriptive Analysis
	Data Integration	No Integration	Partial Integration	Integration with Major Business Entities	Integration with Whole Enterprise	Integration Beyond Enterprise
Smart Products	Digital Twins	There are some implementation projects	There are virtual models in the PLM	Virtual models of the PLM are well updated	Well updated Virtual models of the PLM used product improvement	Well updated Virtual models of the PLM used product improvement, and SAT (Servitization Business Models)

Smart Products	Tracking the product	No products are tracked	Products are tracked within manufacturer	Route of products are tracked until delivery to the customer	Products are tracked throughout their lifecycle	Products routes status is tracked
	ICT adds functionalities	Products have little add-on functionalities	Products feature initial add-on functionalities	Products feature multiple, interrelated add-on functionalities	Products feature add-on functionalities in different areas	Products feature extensive add-on functionalities
	Connectivity and Data Access	No access to product after point of sale	Indirect, situational data, manual customer data exchange	Continuous interconnectivity; mainly reading rights	Continuous interconnectivity; full access to product;	connectivity of the product is a substantial component
	Product-Service System Model	Product offers basic services based on data, without revenues	Product offers services based on data with a periodical payment	Offers a service by pay per use	Offers a service by pay per results	Offers services based on data for improving the result
Smart Operation	Process Control	Instinct-driven Decisions	Data-based Decisions based on data from some functions	Data-based Decisions based on data from across organization	Autonomous Decisions for all functions of organization	Autonomous Decisions for organization and ecosystems partners
	Production Flexibility	Rigid Production Systems	Adaptive Production Systems	Component-driven Production	Modular Production	Modular Production across Value-adding Network
	Product Assembly	Small Proportion of Identical Parts	High Proportion of Identical Parts	Modular Construction of Products	Modular Products	Modular Products across Value-adding Network
	Business Processes Flexibility	Rigid Processes	Flexibility within Individual Processes	Interaction of Processes	Interaction across the Value-adding Network	Interaction across the Value-adding Network
	Inter-organizational Collaboration	Linear Supply Chain	Provider Network	Partner Network	Digital Value-Chain	Digital Ecosystem with Knowledge protection

Smart Operation	Life Cycle Management	Development, production, sale, and shipment; no responsibility for operation	no responsibility for operation but reactive provision of services	Development, production, sale, shipment, maintenance, and usage phase	Responsible for guaranteeing the usability of the product	Managing everything until the end of the product life cycle; responsible for delivering results and productivity
	PSS Design Methods and Tools	No approach for service or PSS development;	Partial use of PSS methods and tools	Selected approaches and formalized development processes for PSS; appropriate tools for development and implementation	Company-specific and individualized PSS approaches plus fast development cycles and prototyping; continuous improvement and use of methods	Company and ecosystem partners PSS approaches plus fast development cycles and prototyping; continuous improvement and share of methods
	Autonomous processes	Machine level: Partial mainly loading/unloading solutions	Machine level: Robots and assistants with more applications	Some production lines are partially automated	Some production lines are highly automated	All production lines are highly automated across the Value-adding Network
	Product Performance Measurement	Only measuring product quality by internal tests	Occasional insights measuring product performance but through maintenance services	Measurement of product performance and usage to guarantee and optimize product availability	Well-defined measures and feedbacks are systematically used for payments, maintenance	Well-defined measures and feedbacks are systematically used for new service development
Smart Factory	IT Infrastructure	Function-specific Infrastructure	Service-oriented Architecture	Cloud based infrastructure is used by some functions	effectively uses cloud-based infrastructure for all functions	effectively use cloud-based infrastructure with ecosystem partners
	IT Security	Isolated IT security activities	Security of Highly Critical Assets	Security of Processes	Intra- and inter-organizational IT security activities	Security by design in product development process
Smart Factory	IT Role	Functional IT	Business Integrated IT	IT as Service Provider	IT as Driver of Change, enabler of product-availability	IT as Driver of Change, enabler of product-performance

	Digital Modelling	Implementation project in a concrete area of the organization	Virtual model of the manufacturing plant is not used or updated	Updated virtual model of the manufacturing plant, it is used to make some incidental simulations	The plant has a digital model for simulations and improvement	The plant has a digital model for simulations and improvement; integrated with the ICT of the organization
	Adaptive & learning capabilities	machinery has a system of alarms	machinery has an alarm and can give some advice to the operator	machinery triggers an alarm and can automatically correct the problem, but with reduced performance	machinery triggers an alarm and can automatically correct the problem and maintain the performance	machinery triggers an alarm and can automatically correct the problem maintaining or improving the performance
Strategy & Organisation	Offering	Product	Standard Service	Novel, additional Services	Product-as-a-Service	Result-as-a-Service
	Pricing Strategy	(Fixed) one-time Price (pay for product)	One-time payment for product and situational service fee	Periodic Fee	Usage-based Billing (pay on availability)	Performance-based Billing (Customer-specific, result-based payment based on service level agreement)
	Sale Channel	Traditional Channels	Traditional and web-based channels for product sales	Traditional and web-based channels for product and service sales	Traditional and web-based channels or product as point of sale	Traditional and web-based channels and product as point of sale for integrated view on results
	Resource Allocation for PSS	No budget for PSS development and implementation	Little effort for creating additional services to the product; ad hoc investments in organizational changes	Medium effort for creating well-functioning PSS; continuous investments	Great efforts for maintaining well-functioning PSS; substantial and continuous investments	Great efforts to achieve a high-performance PSS; substantial and continuous investments
Strategy & Organisation	Partner Integration	Only suppliers as value-adding partners; clear organizational boundaries	Additional value-adding partners for service-creation and initial involvement of customer	Blurring of boundaries between company and suppliers as well as service-creation involved partners; close cooperation with customer as partner	Strong collaboration and integration of value-added partners and customer for PSS co-creation	Deeply integrated into partners and customers' processes, and business model

	Organizational Structure	Function-oriented hierarchical	Structures Cross-functional Projects	Product-/Process-oriented	Organization Independent, self-organized Teams	Organization Independent, self-organized Teams with ecosystem partners
Customer	Customer Insights	No Information	Anonymous Information	Segment-specific Information	Personalized (expectations, preferences) Information	All Personalized Information are actively considered across the Value-adding Network
	Customer Integration	Integration of Feedback	Integration in Early Design Process	Design Process as Co-Creation	Ideation Phase as Co-Creation	Partner-like Collaboration
	Customer Interaction	Interaction focuses on product purchase	Self-Service	PSS provider initiates services and is responsible for ensuring the perpetual availability; planned interactions	Digital, Semi-automated Interaction	Proactive and automated service interaction; connected through pre-defined touch points and processes; result as continuously monitored parameter for service initiative
	Customer Experience	There is no or little personalisation	Some aspects of the customer experience are personalized	Almost aspects of the customer experience are personalized	All aspects of the customer experience are personalized	All aspects of the customer experience are personalized based on collected customer insights and context from both the organization and its ecosystem partners.

Biographies

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